

Communiqué of the e-IRG Workshop
organized in the framework of the Portuguese EU Presidency, 25-26 May 2021

e-IRG Workshop on e-Infrastructures for Climate Change and Digital Transitions

Given the success of the previous workshops organized by the e-IRG in May 2020, and December 2020, it was decided to capitalize on the knowledge and experience of those events, to carry forward the discussion about important topics for the e-Infrastructure community and organise a next virtual workshop within the framework of the Portuguese EU Presidency. The unifying goal of the workshop was to *address the [e-Infrastructures for Climate Change and Digital Transitions](#), ranging from Member States/Associated Countries to European and international level, and from provider to user level*. The event was conducted as a series of three (3) webinars, each of them addressing one of the top challenges the e-infrastructures face in an ever changing and transforming environment. The first webinar session was on *“EOSC data and interoperability”*, the second on *“Addressing climate change – the digital aspects”*, and the third one on *“Going beyond: How policies can shape the development of research infrastructures facilitating data sovereignty, innovation and cultural change”*.

In more detail, the first session introduced the topic of FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs), combining data, code or other research output in one logical entity. A key element of an FDO is a Persistent Identifier (PID), which enables *“unique and persistent identification”* and supports *“referencing, linking, tracing and reusability”*. Furthermore, there is a need for a semantic mapping framework as an addition to the FAIR landscape of semantic artefacts to reap the full benefits of FAIR data. Such e-Infrastructure elements are vital to achieve stability, interoperability and sustainability of the digital objects space, data traceability, trust, and sovereignty. Thus, there is a need for a “by-design” approach and coordination on these e-infrastructures elements. In the session [material](#) there was the pre-recorded presentations of three demonstrators on FDOs that showed how FDOs can help build larger reference implementations.

The first session’s moderator, **Maria – Luisa Lavitrano**, and the speakers, **Peter Wittenburg**, **Maggie Helström** and **Daan Broeder** supported overall the idea that there is a need for: *“An EU-wide service for Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) for all researchers and their stable repositories”*.

The second session was introduced by what could be seen of as an Institutional Open Science Cloud (IOSC) which is located in Chalmers University. The session mainly dealt with the growing importance of e-Infrastructures for society and climate change. On one hand, the digital infrastructures with their computing power and simulations are contributing to *“better understanding the climate future”*, and also *“facilitate tools to fight and reduce some of its effects”*, such as wildfires that caused unprecedented damages in European countries such as Greece and Portugal, but also around the world including Australia, California and Siberia. On the other hand, *“e-Infrastructures have a significant carbon footprint”*, and, thus, Green IT and energy efficient data centres are of particular importance. All presentations and the recordings are available in related session [material](#).

The second session’s moderator, **Irina Kupiainen**, and the speakers, **Sverker Holmgren**, **Thomas Schulthess**, **Stathes Hadjiefthymiades**, **Nuno Lopes**, and **Patrick Gorringe** presented cases where “e-

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infrastructures can help monitor, study, and manage the European forests and seas” through integrated tools and shared data.

The third session concerned the *current status of development of research infrastructures, including e-Infrastructures, which is driven by direct demand or interests, rather than strategic planning.* However, as noted in the previous session, in the face of the upcoming effects of climate change, and other grand challenges, a more *strategic approach to layout the European Research Area is required.* The use of data is central and crucial in this approach.

The third session’s moderator, **Konstantinos Repanas**, and the speakers, **George Strawn**, **Jozsef Györkös**, and **Franciska de Jong** contributed to a *“foresight discussion addressing the data aspects from different angles; the technical prospect, the funders perspective, while still having a human-centric approach”*. In this session the interoperability of data was identified as the hardest to achieve dimension of the FAIR principles. Its realisation would have similar or even stronger impact on science and the world in general as the Internet has. Still, it will take at least a decade until Open Science and FAIR agenda are practiced as the norm:

“When any new technology is available, the status quo always resists its revolutionary potential.”
[George Strawn]

The e-IRG will continue to provide policy recommendations that are also shaped by inputs provided in the e-IRG workshops and further the discussion on the e-Infrastructure Commons.

The e-IRG Workshop was organised within the framework of the Portuguese Presidency of the Council of the European Union by e-IRG and the e-IRG secretariat, with the support of the Portuguese Foundation for National Scientific Computation (FCCN), which is a Unit of the Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT).

The e-IRG Support Programme e-IRGSP6 has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 823761

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